

CHARACTERS AND LANDSCAPE IN THE ADVENTURES OF TOM SAWYER

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Annotation: This article examines the depiction of characters and landscape in Mark Twain’s novel *The Adventures of Tom Sawyer* and their significance in the novel’s artistic structure. The analysis focuses on key characters such as Tom Sawyer, Huckleberry Finn, Becky Thatcher, and Injun Joe through the lens of E. M. Forster’s theory of flat and round characters, assessing their development and transformation. Furthermore, drawing on the perspectives of J. R. R. Tolkien and other literary scholars, the study explores how Twain’s realistic yet vividly imaginative setting enhances reader engagement. By analyzing themes of childhood adventures, personal growth, friendship, and freedom, this paper underscores the novel’s enduring literary value.

Keywords: Mark Twain, *The Adventures of Tom Sawyer*, character analysis, landscape depiction, flat and round characters, realism in literature, childhood adventures, literary imagery, artistic environment.

Characters behave the way they do because of the world they inhabit. The landscapes they long for impact the way they behave. The ones they live in shape

their destiny. Being lifted from the landscape they belong in can unleash elemental forces in a character.¹

Characters and landscape are essential elements of literature. Characters make a story engaging by expressing emotions, overcoming challenges, and learning valuable lessons. Meanwhile, the landscape sets the mood, builds the atmosphere, and shapes the adventure, making the story feel real. Together, these elements immerse readers in the narrative and help them form a deep connection with the story.

The Adventures of Tom Sawyer is the irresistible story of a fourteen-year-old boy growing up in the heartland of America based on the classic novel. Filled with foot-stomping, toe-tapping songs by Don Schlitz ("The Gambler") and a book by Ken Ludwig, this musical adventure is a tale of thrilling escapes, comedy and inspiration for the whole family.

Set in 1840 Missouri, The Adventures of Tom Sawyer is the tale of young Tom Sawyer and the never ending mischief of which he so often finds himself a part of; whether it's matching wits with Aunt Polly, tricking his friends into white-washing a fence for him, or narrowly escaping the clutches of a murderous villain. Along with best friend Huckleberry Finn and love interest Becky Thatcher, the greatest Tom Sawyer exploits are plucked from the book and plopped on the stage.

Aside from having one of the most recognizable titles from literary history, The Adventures of Tom Sawyer is a superb family-friendly show. The large, flexible cast size as well as potential for tying into English curriculums make it an exemplary choice for schools. This also serves as a great opportunity to showcase your male talent.²

E. M. Forster (Aspects of the Novel, 1927) classifies characters as "flat" or "round": "Flat characters are sometimes called types, and round characters are the ones who surprise us with their complexity." This distinction is also useful for analyzing the characters in The Adventures of Tom Sawyer.³

Here, in The Adventures of Tom Sawyer, we compare the depiction of characters and landscapes in the English original and its Uzbek translation.

English: "He saw a new girl in the garden - lovely little blue eyed creature with yellow hair plaited into two long-tails, white summer frock and embroidered pantalettes".(23-page)

¹ Writing Tips: Landscape and Character - Julie Hartley

² MTI Europe <https://www.mtishows.co.uk> The Adventures of Tom Sawyer

³ E. M. Forster (Aspects of the Novel, 1927)

Uzbek:“Tom shu yerdagi bog' ichida notanish bir qizga ko'zi tushdi. Bu qiz oltindek sap-sariq sochlarini ikki o'rim qilib, orqasiga tashlagan,ko'k ko'zli, yozlik oq nafis ko'ylak va guldor ishton kiygan chiroylik bir qizaloq edi”.(26-bet)

Note: "Lovely little blue-eyed creature" vs. "ko‘k ko‘zli... chiroylik bir qizaloq"

The English version uses "creature", which adds a sense of admiration, whereas the Uzbek version directly calls her "qizaloq" (little girl).

"Yellow hair plaited into two long-tails" vs. "oltindek sap-sariq sochlarini ikki o‘rim qilib, orqasiga tashlagan"

The Uzbek translation adds "oltindek" (golden like gold), making the description more poetic.

"White summer frock" vs. "yozlik oq nafis ko‘ylak"

The word "frock" is replaced with "ko‘ylak", which is a culturally appropriate equivalent.

"Embroidered pantalettes" vs. "guldor ishton"

"Pantalettes" were a common undergarment for girls in the 19th century, but the translation uses "ishton", a term more familiar in Uzbek culture.

English: “A good part of the whispering had been occasioned by an event which was more or less rare -entrance visitors: Lawyer Thatcher, accompanied by a very feeble and aged man: a fine, portly, middle aged gentleman with iron-gray hair; and a dignified lady who was doubtless the latter's wife”. (37-bet)

Uzbek: “Gap-so'z va shivir-shivirlarning qo'zg'alishiga ko'pmi-ozmi sabab bo'lgan narsa - kishilarning kelib qishi bo'ldi; Bedarmon bir mo'ysafid chol bilan advokat Techer, ko'rkam o'rta yoshli bir olifta kishi va mahobatli bir xotin kirib keldi. Bu xotin albatta haligi oliftaning xotini bo'lsa kerak”. (41-bet)

Note: "A very feeble and aged man" vs. "Bedarmon bir mo‘ysafid chol"

"Feeble" means weak, and "aged" emphasizes old age. The translation adds "mo‘ysafid" (an Uzbek term specifically for an elderly man) and "bedarmon" (meaning powerless or frail), making it more expressive.

"Fine, portly, middle-aged gentleman with iron-gray hair" vs "Ko‘rkam o‘rta yoshli bir olifta kishi"

"Portly" means slightly stout or heavyset, but the Uzbek translation omits this detail and focuses on "ko‘rkam" (handsome).

The phrase "with iron-gray hair" is missing in the Uzbek version, reducing the character's visual detail.

"Dignified lady who was doubtless the latter’s wife" vs. "Mahobatli bir xotin... albatta haligi oliftaning xotini bo‘lsa kerak"

"Dignified lady" suggests respectability, while "mahobatli" conveys grandeur, which slightly changes the nuance.

"Olifta" (a somewhat playful term for a stylish or pretentious man) replaces "gentleman," which adds a local cultural flavor but slightly alters the tone.

English: The balmy summer air, the restful quiet, the odor of the flowers, and the drowsing murmur of the bees had had their effects, and she was nodding over her knitting for she had no company but the cat, and it was asleep in her lap.(22-page)

Uzbek: Barakali yoz havosi uyda hukm surgan jimjitlik, gullarning xushbo'y hidlari, asalarilarning allalovchi g'o'ng'irlashi Polli xolaga o'z ta'sirini o'tkazar edi: u to'qib o'tirgan ishi ustidan mudrab o'tirar, birdan-bir sherigi bo'lgan mushuk ham uning tizzasida pinakka ketgan edi.(23,24-betlar)

Note: "The balmy summer air" vs. "Barakali yoz havosi"

"Balmy" means mild and pleasant, while "barakali" (literally "blessed" or "fruitful") adds a cultural nuance that isn't in the original.

"The restful quiet" vs. "Uyda hukm surgan jimjitlik"

"Restful quiet" suggests peace and relaxation, whereas the Uzbek version adds "uyda hukm surgan" (ruling over the house), making the quiet seem more dominant.

"The odor of the flowers, and the drowsing murmur of the bees had had their effects"

The translation combines these effects into a simpler phrase:

"Gullarning xushbo'y hidlari, asalarilarning allalovchi g'o'ng'irlashi Polli xolaga o'z ta'sirini o'tkazar edi"

"Had their effects" is actively rewritten into "o'z ta'sirini o'tkazar edi" (exerted influence), making it sound more personal and poetic.

"She was nodding over her knitting" vs. "U to'qib o'tirgan ishi ustidan mudrab o'tirar"

The phrase "to'qib o'tirgan ishi ustidan" explicitly states that she is working, even though "knitting" already implies this.

"She had no company but the cat, and it was asleep in her lap."

The Uzbek version adds emotional depth:

"Birdan-bir sherigi bo'lgan mushuk ham uning tizzasida pinakka ketgan edi."

"Birdan-bir sherigi" ("her only companion") adds a slight sense of loneliness, which the English version does not emphasize as much.

Similarly, J. R. R. Tolkien emphasizes the importance of landscape and setting in *On Fairy-Stories* (1939): "The story-maker proves a successful 'sub-creator.' He makes a Secondary World which your mind can enter."⁴

This table compares the original English text, the Uzbek translation, and my revised version, focusing on differences in meaning and style.

English	Uzbek	My version
Blue-eyed	Ko'k ko'zli	✓
Lovely little	Chiroylik bir	Chiroyli kichkina
A new girl	Notanish bir qizga	Yangi bir qiz
Creature	Qizaloq	✓
With yellow hair	Oltindek sap-sariq	✓
Two long-tails	Ikki o'rim	Ikki uzun o'rim
White summer frock	Yozlik oq nafis ko'ylak	Yozlik oq ko'ylak
Embroidered pantalettes	Guldor ishton	✓
Fine	Ko'rkam	✓
Portly	x	Baquvvat
Middle-aged	O'rta yoshli	✓
Gentleman	Olifta kishi	Janob
Iron-gray hair	x	Kulrang sochli
Dignified	Mahobatli	✓
Lady	Xotin	Xonim
The latter's wife	Haligi oliftaning xotini	Haligi janobning turmush o'rtog'i
Balmy	Barakali	Mayin,yoqimli
Restful quiet	Uyda hukm surgan Jimjitlik	Xotirjam jimjitlik
Drowsing murmur	Allalovchi	✓
Nodding over	Mudrab o'tirar	✓
Asleep	Pinakka ketmloq	Uyquga ketgan

In conclusion, the comparison between the English original and the Uzbek translation reveals key differences in meaning, stylistic choices, and cultural adaptation. While both versions convey the same basic ideas, the translation often enriches the text with additional emotional depth and local nuances. For example, the portrayal of characters and the setting is sometimes more explicit or poetic in the Uzbek version, which enhances the emotional engagement of the reader. Ultimately,

⁴ E. M. Forster (*Aspects of the Novel*, 1927)

these differences demonstrate how translation not only transfers words but also shapes the reader's experience through cultural and linguistic nuances.

Literature review:

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